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Comparative Analysis of the High School Education System between the South Korean State and the Turkish State

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GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

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Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

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EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

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1.Yıldırım Bayezit DELDAL

Associate Professor

Ministry of National Education/St Clemets University

Psychological Counseling Guidance USA President

Mail: y.bayezit1977@gmail.com

Orcid ID: 0000-0002-6561-5933

2. Mincheol CHOI(최민철)

Doctor (PhD)

St Clemets University /PhD Program in Educational Management

Mail: mincheol.choi88@gmail.com

Orcid ID: 0009-0002-4097-9463

ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyze the contrasting education systems of South Korea and Turkey at the high school level, considering the differences that exist in today's world. An academic analysis was conducted to compare the structure, operation, history, and course curriculum of

South Korean high school education with those of the Turkish High School Education system.

Key Words: Education, High School, Curriculum, Turkey, Korea, System, Quality, Structure

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INTRODUCTION

There exist diverse schooling systems across the globe. Provided that subsequent generations have a robust education system encompassing primary, secondary, high school, and university education, they are likely to achieve more success in their future endeavors and professional pursuits. Within the South Korean State Education system, high school education holds significant relevance for the country. Similarly, within the realm of developing and advanced scientific societies, the Turkish State High School Education system plays a crucial role in providing primary education to pupils who will later pursue higher education at the university level. An investigation was conducted on the advancements in the high school education systems of both countries.

AIM

The objective of the study is to conduct a comparative examination of the High School Education System in South Korea and Turkey.

METHOD

When examining the education systems of South Korea and Turkey, a literature review and qualitative research methodologies were employed. Research papers were translated and compiled from various sources including articles, books, conferences, internet data sources, and scientific articles.

RESULTS

HISTORY OF OLD SOUTH KOREA HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATION

Japanese Colonial Period (1910-1945) : From 1910 to 1945, the Korean education system was under to Japanese influence during the Japanese colonial period. Japan exerted control over Korean education, imposing the use of Japanese language and culture, and providing very limited educational possibilities for Korean pupils (K12 Academics).

After Liberation and the Modern Era : Following its liberation in 1945, Korea commenced the process of establishing its own autonomous education system. Following the founding of the Republic of Korea in 1948, there was a significant increase in educational reforms and the scope of compulsory education was increased. Education continued to be seen as a crucial component of national progress even after the conclusion of the Korean War in 1953 (K12 Academics). During the 1960s and beyond, there was a rise in spending in education to bolster economic expansion. In the 1980s, a range of reforms were implemented to enhance access to universities and promote educational equality. In the 1990s, several measures were put into effect to enhance the caliber of education and successfully incorporate educational technology fit for the information age (K12 Academics) (Wikipedia)

Recent Changes: Since the 2000s, Korean high school education has prioritized student-centered curricula with a focus on fostering creativity and critical thinking abilities. The university admission process has undergone multiple revisions, and in 2015, the Free Term application was introduced. This program enables students to engage in diverse career exploration activities (Wikipedia).

The System and Curriculum of South Korean High School Education Today

South Korean National Education Affiliated High School Education System : In Korea, high schools are categorized as ordinary high schools, special-purpose high schools, specialized high schools, and autonomous high schools based on their curriculum administration and level of school autonomy. Irrespective of the categorization of schools, all high school graduates are regarded as having equal academic proficiency. In South Korea, students who do not finish the high school curriculum can still receive academic recognition equivalent to a high school graduate provided they pass the high school graduation qualification exam. Karic

HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATION CURRICULUM OF SOUTH KOREA NATIONAL EDUCATION

Organization and credit allocation standards

1) Organization

A) The high school curriculum is organized into courses (groups) and creative experiential activities.

B) Subjects are general subjects and specialized subjects.

(1) General topics

(A) The general subjects courses (groups) include Korean, mathematics, English, social studies (including history/ethics), science, physical education, art, technology/home economics/knowledge, second foreign language, Chinese characters, and liberal arts.

(B) Typically, courses are categorized into two main types: common courses and elective

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courses. Elective courses are categorized into three types: general elective courses, career elective courses, and convergence elective courses.

(2) Specialized subjects

(a) Subjects (groups) of specializations, with national consideration, are management/finance, health/welfare, culture/art/design/publishing, beauty, tourism/entertainment, food/cooking, architecture/civil engineering, machinery, etc. job qualification standards etc. Topics include materials, chemical industry, textiles/clothing, electrical/electronics, information/communications, environment/safety/firefighting, agriculture/forestry/livestock, fisheries/transportation, convergence/intellectual property.

(B) Subjects in specialized subjects are divided into specialized common subjects, basic general subjects and basic practical subjects.

c) Examples of creative experiential activities encompass self-directed activities, club-based activities, and career-oriented activities. Guidelines pertaining to the structure and functioning of the curriculum

1) Common topics

A) The high school curriculum mandates a total of 192 credits, with 174 credits allocated to classes and 18 credits (equivalent to 288 hours) dedicated to creative experiential activities.

B) The school arranges the subjects that students can finish in a span of three years, using a semester-based system, and provides information to both students and parents.

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C) The school proactively disseminates information regarding elective courses, in tandem with career and academic design guidance, to enable students to enroll in courses that are pertinent to their chosen professions.

D) The school has autonomous control over the regulation and administration of course completion times and credits. However, please adhere to the following guidelines.

(1) The institution is structured and managed in a manner that allows students to successfully finish courses on a semester basis.

(2) Typically, foundational subjects are arranged and conducted prior to the completion of elective courses in the corresponding subject area.

(3) Considering the student's level of development, it is possible to arrange and instruct Basic Mathematics 1, 2 and Basic English 1, 2 courses instead of Common Mathematics 1, 2 and Common English 1, 2. Exact information regarding this matter will be in line with the criteria set by the city/county superintendent of education.

(4) Elective courses are organized in a hierarchical manner to guarantee that learning occurs in a sequential order. Nevertheless, it can be structured and managed with adaptability in accordance with the specific circumstances of the school, the requirements of the students, and the characteristics of the subject matter.

E) The institution effectively manages the number of credits acquired per semester to alleviate the academic workload of students and facilitate in-depth learning.

F) The school limits the number of credits obtained in special-purpose higher elective courses in special-purpose high schools to prevent students from earning more credits than necessary for their academic load and needs. Only the following schools, including specialized high schools and high schools tailored to meet industrial needs, are available. You are only allowed to enroll in supplementary courses in specialized fields.

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G) If a minimum number of students express their desire to offer elective courses in this curriculum, the school is required to provide these courses. Exact information regarding this will be in line with the directives set by the city/county superintendent of education.

H) The school endeavors to enhance students' options for completing elective courses through various means, while adhering to the following criteria.

(1) If a student desires to enroll in an elective course that is not available at their current school, it is permissible for them to fulfill that course requirement at another educational institution that provides the desired course. The specific specifics pertaining to this matter will adhere to the rules set forth by the superintendent of education of the city/county.

(2) If deemed essential, the school has the option to introduce new courses in addition to the ones already outlined in this curriculum. In this scenario, it is imperative to carry out the required procedures beforehand, following the guidelines established by the provincial director of national education.

(3) The school acknowledges the fulfillment of extracurricular education offered by community organizations as a subject or creative experiential activity, based on the individual requirements of the student. The specific information pertaining to this matter will be in conformity with the rules set forth by the city or provincial superintendent of education.

(4) Schools have the option to provide college courses that have prerequisite courses and follow internationally recognized curricula or subjects, if they are considered required. The specific information pertaining to this matter will adhere to the rules set forth by the city/county superintendent of education.

I) The school independently plans and manages creative experiential activities, considering the student's developmental stage and school resources. It also ensures the implementation of diverse activities according to the student's career path and abilities.

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J) The school acknowledges the acquisition of credits when the student fulfills the requirements for both curricular and creative experience activities. The completion requirements are established to accurately represent the attendance rate and academic success rate. The particular details pertaining to this matter are determined by the rules established by the Ministry of Education.

K) Schools offer preventive and supplemental guidance in many forms to ensure the minimum level of achievement for each topic, taking into consideration the characteristics of the school.

L) The school arranges and carries out career-focused training that enhances the linkage between academic levels and vocational education during the transitional phase.

(1) The school independently provides job-oriented education, using the curriculum and dedicated experience activity time to assist students in designing their professional and academic paths.

(2) The curriculum incorporates creative experience activities to foster an awareness of university life, prerequisite courses, social life guidance, and adaptation exercises throughout the journey towards graduation.

M) Schools have the option to establish specialized educational programs for pupils who meet the criteria for special education, if it is deemed essential. In this scenario, it is structured as either a career elective or a convergence elective.

2) General High School

A) A total of 84 credits out of the 174 credits in subjects (groups) need to be finished. If deemed necessary, factors such as the school, the student's career trajectory, and their level of growth will be taken into consideration. The credit requirements may vary for each student and will be calculated according to the rules established by the education inspector of the city/province.

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B) The school structures its curriculum based on broad courses, but is also capable of offering specialized studies as needed. In this instance, it is structured as a vocational elective course.

C) If a school decides to introduce a second foreign language course, it is imperative that they make an effort to simultaneously offer two or more courses.

D) If deemed necessary, the school may introduce a new subject that is not currently included in the curriculum. This subject will be structured as either a career elective course or a convergence elective course.

E) Schools have the option to establish focus schools that concentrate on particular disciplines, allowing for a specialized curriculum. It is advisable to allocate more than 30% of the autonomous credits to the applicable course (group) in accordance with the rules established by the metropolitan/provincial director of education.

F) Schools have the authority to form and manage departments that are specifically focused on vocational education, or they can offer vocational training courses. In this scenario, the criteria for distributing credits to specialized high schools and high schools that cater to industry needs can be utilized. The particular guidelines for this process are established based on the principles set by the director of national education in the metropolitan or provincial area.

3) Specialized high schools (excluding those specifically designed for industrial needs)

A) A minimum of 75 credits out of a total of 174 credits in the subject (group) must be completed. Additionally, more than 68 credits of the available independent credits are designated as elective courses that are relevant to the specialized high school major.

B) The excluded courses adhere to the curriculum of comparable courses. If there is a need to create a new department and develop its curriculum, it is essential to follow the predetermined principles set by the provincial director of national education and complete the required procedures in advance.

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C) Schools have the ability to offer specialized courses as needed. In this instance, it is structured as a career optional course.

D) If deemed necessary, the school may introduce a new subject that is not currently included in the curriculum. This subject will be structured as either a career elective course or a convergence elective course.

4) Specialized high schools and high schools tailored to meet the needs of the industrial sector.

A) The school establishes departments based on industry demands and workforce trends. It offers a curriculum that focuses on developing fundamental vocational skills and business acumen. The curriculum is tailored to the specific needs of each department, with a focus on enhancing students' employability and career growth. The event was efficiently planned and executed.

(1) The total number of credits necessary for subjects (groups) is 174. Out of these, 64 credits are required for general subjects and 80 credits are required for specialty courses. If deemed essential, the school has the authority to assess the student's career trajectory and degree of progress, among other factors, in order to determine the appropriate credit requirements for each individual student. The particular rules for this evaluation will be defined by the superintendent of education in your school's city or county.

(2) Schools have the ability to arrange and carry out specialized subjects by choosing courses from many disciplines or groupings.

(3) Schools have the ability to arrange and carry out specialized core subjects that are mandatory for all students, taking into account the specific circumstances of the school and the requirements of the students.

(4) The teaching and learning of core applied disciplines adhere to the accomplishment requirements set by the National Proficiency requirements. These subjects are assessed based on competency units, which represent specific content areas.

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B) If deemed necessary, the school has the authority to develop a comprehensive major, minor, or qualifying course while managing a department. The specific specifics pertaining to this matter will adhere to the rules set forth by the superintendent of education of the city or county.

C) Opting for and successfully finishing a foundational subject that is necessary for a specialized subject can be seen as fulfilling an elective requirement within the corresponding broad subject area.

D) Elective courses in general subjects can be established and managed by modifying the contents of specialized courses that have comparable or related content. In this scenario, it is imperative to carry out the required procedures beforehand, following the guidelines set by the provincial director of national education.

E) Schools have the ability to organize the curriculum by incorporating specialized subjects or content aspects that align with the specific needs of the industry. However, for key applied topics, it is necessary to adhere to national job competency standards. In this regard, specific content areas (competency units) can be chosen and implemented based on the requirements of the school and the students.

F) Field trainings are incorporated into the curriculum to facilitate the practical application of knowledge and skills acquired in school. These trainings aim to provide diverse professional experiences and enhance the ability to adapt to real-world situations.

(1) Field education is implemented to provide students with practical exposure to curriculum-related tasks. Specifically, students have the option to decide whether or not they want to take part in industry-based field training. However, the school and industry collaborate to create a field training program and assess the progress and outcomes of the training.

(2) Field training can be conducted through collaboration with local community organizations, following the guidelines established by the provincial director of national education.

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G) When teaching disciplines that include hands-on training, it is important for the school to offer comprehensive instruction on occupational health and safety that is directly relevant to the course material. Additionally, the school should take precautionary steps, such as installing safety equipment, to ensure the safety of the students.

H) Engaging in innovative hands-on activities can enhance students' career trajectory and professional prospects, foster personal growth, and enhance their marketability.

Adheres to the curriculum for comparable disciplines. Prior to the development of a new course or group, and the subsequent organization and administration of the curriculum, it is imperative to complete the required procedures in accordance with the standards set by the provincial director of national education.

J) If a school wishes to introduce a new major applied subject alongside its existing curriculum, it must adhere to national employment proficiency criteria and complete the required procedures beforehand. It is imperative to adhere to the principles established by the Metropolitan/Provincial Director of National Education.

K) High schools that have adjusted to meet the needs of the industrial sector are granted the freedom to independently design and execute their curriculum. This allows for the creation of a tailored curriculum that directly aligns with the demands of the industry. However, certain matters pertaining to this are regulated by guidelines set by provincial or district inspectors. (Ministry of National Education Communiqué No. 2022-33) This communiqué provides information on the overall and specific components of primary and high school curricula.

Establishment of High Schools in Turkey

The education reform initiated during the final stages of the Ottoman Empire subsequently evolved into a national endeavor during the Republic of Turkey. During the most challenging days of the War of Independence, efforts were made to address and resolve education-related

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issues. On May 9, 1920, precisely sixteen days after the formation of the Turkish Grand National Assembly, the government announced in parliament that, although they were unable to implement significant changes due to the ongoing war, they aimed to enact measures to enhance national awareness as soon as the war concluded. (Özalp, 1983: 106) During a time when the War of Independence was at its most ferocious and the enemy was advancing towards the Sakarya River, the matter of education was not overlooked. On 15 July 1921, the Education Congress was held, with the opening speech delivered by Mustafa Kemal himself. The sources cited include Akyüz (1983: 89), Alicigüzel (1973: 150), and İnan (1983: 62).

During the congress's inaugural speech, Mustafa Kemal Pasha expressed his belief that the education and training systems used thus far had played a pivotal role in shaping our nation's history. When I refer to a national education program, I am specifically talking about a system that aligns with our country's unique characteristics and historical background. This program should be free from outdated superstitions, foreign concepts that are unrelated to our inherent qualities, and any influences from both Eastern and Western cultures. The complete realization of our national brilliance can only be attained through the cultivation of such a cultural environment. A resolute and well-defined foreign culture can lead to the replication of the detrimental outcomes associated with the foreign cultures that have been adhered to thus far. In this congress, our objective is not only to ponder over the conventional path of treading on the established routes, but also to discover a novel approach to art and creativity that aligns with the criteria I have outlined, and to present it to the nation. We anticipate a reverential ceremony that will serve as a demonstration to the world and act as a guiding force to steer the current generation along that particular road... (Akyüz, 1983: 92–93; Yücel, 1994: 20–21)

During his inaugural address to the Turkish Grand National Assembly on March 1, 1922, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk stated that the primary objective of secondary education is to cultivate skilled professionals in the fields of service and art that are essential for the country, as well as to equip them as potential candidates for advanced study. It is imperative to educate our children and young people at all educational levels about the need of combating any factors that pose a

threat to Turkey's future, its unique identity, and its national traditions. He stated that communities comprised of individuals who are deprived of life and independence lack these essential qualities. (Özalp-Ataünal, 1983: 108)

When examining Mustafa Kemal's lectures on education, it becomes apparent that he placed significant emphasis on matters pertaining to secondary education and shown a keen understanding of the needs and demands of his era. He also desired the establishment of a comprehensive national education system. The reference "Aydemir 2014:165-166" indicates the source of information.

Aims of Turkish Secondary Education Institutions

Secondary education institutions in Turkey operate in accordance with the overall and specific objectives and fundamental principles of Turkish national education, in compliance with universal law, democracy, and human rights. They conduct their activities with a student-centered approach, emphasizing active learning and fostering a democratic organizational culture. The General Directorate of Secondary Education oversees secondary education institutions, which encompass five different sorts of schools: Anatolian high schools, science high schools, fine arts high schools, social sciences high schools, and sports high schools. Secondary education institutions.

- The goal is to enhance students' physical, mental, moral, spiritual, social, and cultural traits, foster respect for democracy and human rights, and equip them with the knowledge and skills necessary for the future.
- The goal of secondary education is to equip students with a broad foundation of knowledge and skills that will prepare them for higher education, professional careers, and success in various aspects of life and business.
- In order to establish a robust, equitable, and dynamic framework for education and employment relations, in line with the principles and policies of the Ministry,
- In order to cultivate pupils' self-assurance, self-discipline, and accountability, • To instill in

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students the practice of diligence and cooperation,

- Facilitating students' acquisition of a foreign language proficiency that allows them to comprehend and keep up with global advancements and transformations,
- Empowering students to generate knowledge via the creation of projects that utilize their knowledge and skills.

Our objectives include delivering high-quality education through the utilization of technology, promoting lifelong learning among individuals, adhering to international standards in training, production, and service, and promoting certification.

- The objective is to enhance students' understanding and proficiency in research, development, and design. Furthermore, science high schools specialize on the disciplines of physics and mathematics, whereas social science high schools focus on cultivating pupils as scholars in the areas of literature and social sciences.

- Fine arts high schools offer students fundamental knowledge and skills in fine arts and serve as a training ground for producing qualified individuals in the field of fine arts.
- Sports high schools strive to equip students with fundamental knowledge and skills in physical education and sports, with the goal of producing qualified individuals in the field of physical education and sports.

The text refers to the General Directorate of Secondary Education within the Ministry of National Education.

Türkiye Secondary Education Current Curriculum

Turkey Century Education Model Trainer Trainings: The Ministry of National Education has launched training sessions for teachers on the "Turkish Century Education Model," led by academicians and field professionals involved in the development of new programs. The new curriculum, developed as part of the Turkey Century Education Model, will be introduced gradually, commencing on September 9, 2024, coinciding with the commencement of the 2024-2025 academic year. The implementation will begin with pre-school, followed by

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the 1st grade of primary school, the 5th grade of secondary school, and the 9th grade of high school.

The Ministry of Education's General Directorate of Teacher Training and Development has developed a thorough training program for all subject teachers whose curriculum has been updated, to ensure successful implementation of the new curriculum. The initial training for teachers commenced with the "Turkish Century Education Model trainer training course".

In this context, initially, over 9 thousand educators will participate in the Turkey Century Education Model trainer training course, which will span 40 hours over the period of one week. There are a total of 61 distinct course programs that have been scheduled for trainer training. The teacher training classes for the new curriculum will conclude on June 14, coinciding with the end of the academic year. The news is from the TR General Directorate of National Education.

Common Text of Turkey Century Maarif Model Curriculum : The General Directorate of Secondary Education, on 26/04/2024, issued a document with reference number E-21658195-101.02-101123899. This document establishes the guidelines for all current and future curricula.

The adoption of the "Common Text on Curriculums" was discussed by our Board in response to the letter from the General Directorate of Secondary Education dated 17/05/2024, with reference number E-21658195-101.02-102573441.

Mathematics Lesson (Preparatory, Grades 9-12) The curriculum will be introduced in secondary education institutions, beginning in the academic year 2024-2025. The implementation will be gradual, starting with the preparatory and 9th grade, as outlined in the attached example.

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The Physics Course is designed for students in grades 9 through 12. Commencing from the 2024-2025 academic year, the curriculum will be introduced in secondary education institutions, beginning with the 9th grade. This information is based on the provided sample.

The Chemistry Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) will offer an education and training program for the 2024-2025 academic year. Commencing from the 9th grade in secondary educational institutions, beginning from the current academic year, please submit your application following the provided example.

The 2024-2025 Education Program for the Biology Course is designed for students in Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12. It will be implemented at secondary education institutions, beginning from the academic year. The program will be followed in a sequential manner, as demonstrated in the attached sample.

- Course on historical events and topics for students in grades 9, 10, and 11. 2024-2025 Curriculum

Commencing from the 9th grade in secondary educational institutions, beginning from the current academic year, please submit your application according to the provided example.

The attached sample outlines the step-by-step 2024-2025 education program for the Geography Course, which is designed for students in Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12 in secondary education institutions.

In the academic years 2025-2026, the Philosophy Course will provide instruction and training for students in the 10th and 11th grades. Education program Commencing from the 10th grade at secondary educational institutions, there is a progressive initiation commencing from the academic year.

Application in accordance with the provided example,

- Turkish Language and Literature Course offered for students in 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th grades as part of their preparatory education. Commencing from the academic year 2024-2025,

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there will be a teaching program available for secondary education. Institutions and their implementation gradually begin from the 9th grade, as seen in the attached example.

- In the 12th grade, students in the Republic of Turkey study the History of Revolution and Kemalism in the year 2027. Course of study Commencing in the academic year of 2028, the enclosed sample will be implemented at secondary education establishments. As per; Approved by the resolution of the Board of Education and Discipline on January 19, 2018, with the reference number 32.

- Mathematics course for secondary education including grades 9, 10, 11, and 12. The curriculum in secondary education institutions will undergo gradual changes starting from the 2024-2025 academic year, beginning with the 9th grade. These changes will involve a reduction in practical components.

The decision to adopt was made by the Board of Education and Discipline on 22/06/2016, with a reference number of 36 2024-2025. Curriculum for Mathematics Course in Secondary Education Preparatory Class It has been adopted in secondary school institutions starting with the academic year of removal.

The Board of Education and Discipline's document, dated 19/01/2018 and identified as number 33, was approved.

The High School Mathematics Course, including grades 9 through 12, will be introduced in secondary education institutions starting from the 2024-2025 academic year.

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Discontinued in practice,

The Secondary Education Physics Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) was approved by the Board of Education and Discipline on 19/01/2018, as stated in decision number 28. Academic Program for the Year 2024-2025 Starting from the academic year, the practice of including the 9th grade in secondary education institutions has been phased out.

The Board of Education and Discipline's document dated 19/01/2018 and numbered 29 was approved.

Physics course offered for students in grades 9, 10, 11, and 12 in high school. Academic Plan for the Year 2024-2025 Beginning in the 9th grade of secondary education institutions, starting from the academic year, the practice was gradually discontinued.

The Secondary Education Chemistry Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) was approved by the Board of Education and Discipline on 19/01/2018, under decision number 30. The curriculum for the 2024 academic year will include changes in secondary education institutions, namely for students in the 9th grade. These changes will involve a progressive reduction in practical components, beginning in the 2025 academic year.

The Board of Education and Discipline's resolution, dated 19/01/2018 and identified as number 31, was approved.

Chemistry course offered for students in grades 9, 10, 11, and 12 in high school. Academic Plan for the year 2024-2025 Beginning in the 9th grade in secondary school institutions, starting with the academic year, the practice was gradually eliminated.

The Secondary Education Biology Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) was approved by the Board of Education and Discipline on 19/01/2018, under decision number 34. The Curriculum 2024 entails the gradual elimination of practical components in secondary education institutions, commencing from the 2025 academic year, beginning with students in the 9th grade.

The Board of Education and Discipline's resolution, dated 19/01/2018 and numbered 35, was approved.

Biology course offered for students in grades 9, 10, 11, and 12 in high school. Academic Plan for the year 2024-2025 Starting from the academic year, the practice of including the 9th grade in secondary education institutions has been phased out.

The decision numbered 36, adopted by the Board of Education and Discipline on 19/01/2018, was changed by our Board with its decision numbered 13 on 26/04/2023.

Course on the history of secondary education for students in grades 9, 10, and 11. Academic Plan for the year 2024-2025 Beginning in the 9th grade in secondary school institutions, starting from the academic year, the practice has been gradually eliminated.

The Secondary Education Geography Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) was approved by the Board of Education and Discipline on January 19, 2018, under decision number 26. The curriculum for the 2024 academic year will include changes in secondary education institutions, namely for students in the 9th grade. These changes will involve a progressive reduction in practical components, beginning in the 2025 academic year.

The Secondary Education Philosophy Course (Grades 10 and 11) was approved by the Board of Education and Discipline through Decision No. 27 on 19/01/2018. Curriculum for the academic year 2025-2026 Beginning in the 10th grade in secondary school institutions, starting from the academic year, the practice has been gradually eliminated.

The Board of school and Discipline, in its decision dated 19/01/2018 and numbered 39, have approved the implementation of the Secondary Education Turkish Language and Literature Course (Grades 9, 10, 11, and 12) Teaching Program in secondary school, starting from the 2024-2025 academic year. Progressively phasing out the practice in educational establishments, commencing from the 9th grade,

The decision numbered 92, dated 27/06/2018, was adopted by the Board of Education and Discipline. Curriculum for the Turkish Language and Literature course in the Secondary Education Preparatory Class Starting from the 2024-2025 academic year, secondary school institutions will require applications.

The decision numbered 45, dated 19/01/2018, was adopted by the Board of Education and Discipline. The curriculum for the History of Revolution and Kemalism course in secondary education institutions in the Republic of Turkey will be discontinued, starting from the 2028 academic year.

The General Directorate of Basic Education was approved to prepare and use teacher guidebooks and educational equipment in line with the Preschool Education Program. Additionally, the relevant general directorates were authorized to create educational tools

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specifically for the academic year when the curriculum for these courses was first implemented. The text refers to a decision made by the Curriculum Board of the Ministry of National Education in Turkey.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The shared objectives of high school education are evident in both countries. The high school program in Korea consists of two types of courses: standard courses and vocational courses. Regular lessons include subjects such as Ethics, Korean Language, Chinese, Mathematics, Society, Science Education, Discipline Course, Music, Art, Vocational Course, Family Course, Foreign Language, and Etiquette. The curriculum in Turkish high schools differs based on the department, which can be categorized as Literature, Boarding, Science, or Mathematics. In Korea, vocational education at the high school level is categorized into many business branches, which is not the case in Turkey. These departments are established based on the country's need and also provide training for the skilled workforce of the nation. Weekly class durations at Korean high schools are a minimum of 34 hours. Elective courses account for 2.94% of the total number of hours spent on courses in secondary school. The reference "Cho 1997:131-132" indicates the specific pages (131-132) in the work by Cho published in 1997.

A database comparison is conducted based on multiple sources as outlined below.

Education time

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South Korea: High school education in South Korea lasts 3 years. Students receive education from the 10th grade (high school 1st grade) to the 12th grade (high school 3rd grade).

Türkiye: High school education in Turkey lasts 4 years. Students study from 9th grade to 12th grade.

Examination system

South Korea: The university admission system in South Korea is primarily categorized into two parts: 'susi' (early application) and 'jeongsi' (general examination). Susi (early application) is a selection technique used by colleges to choose candidates based on their high school grades, personal statements, and interviews. Jeongsi, also known as the general examination, is a selection process where students are chosen based on their performance in the university entrance examination called 'suneung' (대학수학능력시험).

Turkey: The university entrance system in Turkey is bifurcated into two categories: LGS and YKS.

The LGS, or High School Passage Exam, is a test that takes place upon completion of secondary school and determines admission into high school. The YKS, or Higher Education Institutions Exam, is a comprehensive assessment for admission to universities. It is divided into three stages: the TYT, or Basic Proficiency Test, the AYT, or Field Proficiency Test, and the YDT, or Foreign Language Test.

Educational content

CURRENT SCIENCE

South Korea: The high school curriculum in South Korea comprises mandatory subjects such as Korean, mathematics, English, science, social studies, and optional courses. From the second year onwards, students have the option to enroll in elective courses that align with their personal interests and career aspirations.

Turkey: The high school curriculum in Turkey comprises mandatory subjects such as Turkish, mathematics, science, social sciences, foreign language, and optional courses. From the 11th grade onwards, students have the opportunity to focus their studies on certain subjects such as science, social sciences, language, and more.

Private schools

South Korea has specialized schools catering to individuals with particular abilities and distinct sorts of high schools. Special Talent Schools offer focused instruction in specific disciplines such as art, sports, science, and more.

Authentic high schools prioritize students' autonomy and provide a diverse range of educational offerings.

Turkey: There exist diverse categories of private secondary schools in Turkey. Vocational high schools prioritize technical and vocational education. Anatolian High Schools offer a comprehensive academic curriculum that aims to equip pupils with the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed in university. Fine Arts High Schools offer specialized instruction in several artistic disciplines such as music and painting.

Special education

CURRENT SCIENCE

In South Korea, private teaching institutes and academies are prevalent. A significant number of students enhance their preparation for university exams by enrolling in supplementary courses offered by external institutions.

In Turkey, students have the option to pursue supplementary education through private teaching institutes or private sessions, however this practice is less prevalent compared to South Korea.

Comparison of High School Education Systems in South Korea and Turkey and Improvement Suggestions

The high school education systems of South Korea and Turkey are tailored to meet the distinct educational requirements and cultural attributes of each country. This comparison enables us to comprehend the advantages and disadvantages of both systems and pinpoint potential areas for enhancement in future development.

South Korea's Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths

South Korea is globally recognized for its exceptional academic performance, which is attributed to its rigorous academic standards. The exceptional academic achievements of pupils in international examinations serve as a testament to the efficacy of the education system. Diverse educational opportunities are available through specialized talent schools and distinctive high schools, allowing pupils to pursue education in specific areas of interest.

Weaknesses:

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Intense Academic Pressure: The process of taking university entrance tests imposes significant stress on students. This could have a detrimental impact on the overall welfare of pupils. The cost of private education in South Korea is exorbitant, resulting in educational disparities.

Turkey's Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths:

Comprehensive instruction: High schools in Turkey provide a wide-ranging curriculum that allows pupils to get instruction in diverse subjects.

Vocational Education Opportunities: Vocational high schools are crucial in equipping students with the essential skills required for specific occupations.

Weaknesses:

Centralized Education System: The centralization of education might pose challenges in accommodating local requirements.

Restricted Private Education: The availability of private tutoring and supplementary educational options is not as widespread as in South Korea, perhaps leading to inadequate support for certain pupils.

Improvement Suggestions

For South Korea:

By implementing reforms to the university entrance system, it is possible to alleviate exam pressure and provide students with a more well-rounded educational experience.

Educational equity can be enhanced by the reduction of private education expenses and the provision of increased assistance in public schools.

For Türkiye:

Decentralizing education policy allows for the development of policies that are more aligned with the specific demands of local communities. This can more effectively address the specific requirements of schools and pupils. Expanding the availability of private educational institutions and additional educational possibilities might enhance students' access to support and improve their academic achievements.

Joint Development Areas

Both countries have the potential to enhance their utilization of digital education technologies. Enhancing access to resources for both educators and learners can lead to an improvement in the overall quality of education.

Psychosocial support: Greater emphasis should be placed on the psychological and social growth of pupils, with corresponding assistance offered in these domains. Education encompasses more than only achieving academic success; it should also prioritize the holistic development of pupils.

Conclusively, although the high school education systems of South Korea and Turkey possess their unique merits, there are also areas that necessitate enhancement. Considering these advantages and disadvantages, officials and stakeholders in both nations should collaborate to enhance the inclusivity, equilibrium, and student-centeredness of respective education systems.

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Not only will this enhance the academic performance of individual pupils, but it will also elevate the overall standard of education and societal welfare.

This Research consists of 5166 words.

RESTRICTION

In the research, it was recorded by examining the High School Education systems of Korea and Türkiye.

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